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Philosophy of Tantric Buddhism in Orissa

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Introduction

In the historical evolution of Buddhism, Mahayāna with its more liberal doctrine and generous ideal of the final goal was altruistic and highly philosophical and thereby could capture the minds of the people to a greater extent than Hinayāna and gained rapid popularity. Tantrayāna, the latest phase of Buddhism was the combined form of Vajrayāna, Sahajayāna and Kālachakrayāna. It evolved a deep esoteric practice although it was representing the subtle philosophy of Mahayāna in outline. Orissa played an important role in the growth and development of each of these three phases of Buddhism.

It is a known fact that Buddha did not visit Orissa (known as Utkal, Kalinga and Odra in the long past) as no information in support of his visit is available in the old or later works of Buddhism. But Kalinga was not unknown to him for it is revealed from some Chinese sources that he declared Kalinga as one of the twelve places where perfection could be easily attained.¹ Besides, his religion was quite known to the people of Utkala as this was the home land of two merchant brothers named Tapassu and Bhallika, who were the first lay-disciples of Buddha² and erected two magnificent stūpas known as Keśastūpa and Nakhastūpa.³

After Buddha's *mahāparinirvāṇa* there arose disputes among the monks regarding the relaxation of some strict Vinaya-rules. This led at last to a schism during the second Council at Vaisali and thus came into existence two separate schools of Buddhism - Hīnayāna and Mahāsāṅghika. The Mahāsāṅghikas were the fore-runners of Mahayānism.

In Orissa Hīnayāna Buddhism was in prominence as late as the 7th century A.D. Some famous teachers appeared among the Hinayānists by the time, although king Harsavardhana was eager to discredit the Hinayānists in Orissa. There flourished in Orissa Prājñāgupta, a great teacher of Hinayānic faith in the late 6th century A.D., who composed a treatise of 700 śloka dogmatically challenging the Mahayānic system. This was considered to be a great authentic work by the Hinayānic priests of Orissa, who presented the same to the king Harsavardhana as a boastful challenge.⁴

The most important change in thought and outlook of Mahayāna as contrasted with Hīnayāna is the conception of final goal. According to the Hīnayānists the Arhathood or the final liberation of the self from the whirl of existence is to be

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achieved through strict ethical discipline and the process of dhyāna or meditation. To them Buddha was only a historical personage or an arhat and superior to Bhahmā, Viṣṇu and Indra. The Hīnayānic conception finds expression in the Anguttar Nikāya in the following manner - "He is neither a god, nor a Gandharvā, nor a Yakṣa, he is Buddha."⁵ The Mahāsāṅghika school, however, maintained a very different conception of Buddhology. The allusion available in Hīnayānic scriptures as to the spiritual entity of Buddha found vigorous expression in the Mahāsāṅghika texts.

In subsequent time other ideas appeared on the horizon and the new literature of Mahāyāna called pāramitā sprang up. The ideas of pāramitās gradually effected a drastic change in thought and outlook of Buddhism and thus paved the way for the growth of a vastly developed literature named Prajñāpāramitā. The Prajñāpāramitās are of a great importance in ascertaining the origin and development of Mahāyāna Buddhism. Hence the time and place of the composition of the earliest Prajñāpāramitā may be tentatively taken as the actual time and place of origin of Mahāyāna.

The popular hold of Mahāyāna Buddhism in Orissa can be shown by throwing some light on the historical growth of the magnificent monasteries and other centres of Mahāyāna Buddhism which were truly the seats of culture and education in Orissa and the learned sages and philosophers used to impart both religious and secular instructions to the people and the scholars in these monastic institutions. The Gaṇḍavyūha, a purely Mahāyānic text of the 3rd century A.D., gives a vivid description of the city of Tosali, where there was a hill named Surabhogiri with a monastic establishment, with which the renowned sage Sarvagāmin was associated.⁶

Mahāyāna Buddhism, as already discussed, was more catholic than Hīnayāna and the apostles of Mahayana had to make it so to attract all sorts of people of the society. For all those people, who were of different tastes and intellectual calibre, it was necessary to make suitable provisions within the fold of Mahāyāna Buddhism. For this reason heterogeneous elements of faith and religious practices began to creep into Buddhism in general and Mahāyāna in particular.

The less-advanced or ordinary followers of Buddhism could not follow the original aphorism of Buddhism and for them it was felt necessary to abridge Sūtra into Dhāraṇī, which is an element of Mantra and whose literal meaning is that by which something is sustained or kept up (dhāryate anayā iti) i.e. the mystic syllable capable of keeping up man's religious life which is known as the synonym of the term Rakṣa in Sanskrit. These ordinary followers had to commit to memory and recite the Dhāraṇīs regularly which, they were convinced, were in possession of immense power to produce infinite merit in the reciters and conferring desired benefit on them.

When some elements of Tantrism in the form of dhāraṇī, mantra, mudrā, maṇḍala, etc. were allowed to make their way into Buddhism, many other traditional beliefs in magic, charms and sorceries with all their accessories began to rush quickly into it, as a result of which the composite system of the religion changed the colour and tone of the later Mahāyāna to the extent of evolving a new Yāna, which is popularly known as Tantrayāna. Thus Tantrayāna which is used in a general sense for Tantric Buddhism grew within the province of Mahāyāna or in other words Mahāyāna was the introductory stage of Tantric Buddhism and the later phase of Mahāyāna witnessed the full-fledged development of Tantric Buddhism. Incidentally Tantric Buddhism incorporated within it the sexo-yogic practices, the six kinds of esoteric rituals technically referred to as abhichāra, the five accessories known as pañcha-ma-kāra etc. The sexo-yogic practices came to be regarded as the most important esoteric practices for the attainment of the final state of supreme bliss, all other practices being held as preparatory accessories. The six types of esoteric rituals or abhichāra are intended for the good or evil of anybody especially for the purpose of fulfilment of the desires of sādhanas. Those are mārana (killing), mohana (enchanting), sthambhana (paralysing), vidveṣana (envying or rendering harm through animosity), ucchātana (exciting) and vaśīkarana (subduing). The pañcha-ma-kāra or the five m's include madya (wine), māmsa (meat), matsya (fish), mudrā (parched cereal/woman) and maithuna (sexual intercourse).⁷

From the full-fledged development of Tantric Buddhism all other offshoots like Vajrayāna,

Sahajayāna and Kālacakrayāna arose. There is difference of opinion among the scholars as to the chronology of these three later schools. All scholars agree in giving Vajrayāna the earlier place; but they differ in placing Sahajayāna and Kālacakrayāna in sequence of time. Dr. B. Bhattacharyya and Dr. P.C. Bagchi suggest that Sahajayāna developed earlier than Kālacakrayāna,⁸ while Dr. S.B. Dasagupta and Dr. N.K. Sahu maintain that Kālacakrayāna preceded Sahajayana.⁹ The latter group of scholars have contributed erudite discourses through the pages of their books on these schools regarding the order of development. But so far as the historical evolution of these latter schools is concerned, the order suggested by the former scholars seems to be correct. The propounders of Vajrayāna, Sahajayāna and Kālacakrayāna were Indrabhuti, Lakṣminkarā and Pitopāda respectively, all of them belonged to Uddiyāna, the same as Orissa and historically they are given the position in the orders of chronology - Indrabhuti, Lakṣminkarā and Pitopāda.

Vajrayāna

Literally the term Vajrayāna is the 'adamantine path or vehicle', but technically it means 'Sūnya Vehicle' where Sūnya is used in a special sense to represent Vajra. Sūnya is called Vajra for the reason that "it is firm, sound, unaltered, unpierceable, impenetrable, incombustible and indestructible."¹⁰ The Sūnya referred to by the Vajrayānists in all their writings is not the exact Sūnya as conceived by the Mādhyamikas to whom both the subject and the object are Sūnya in essence, and neither mind nor the external world bear any reality.¹¹ This aspect was not, however, acceptable by the Vajrayānists; because they were in search of a positive aspect in the Sūnyatā. In the sādhanamālā the word Vajrayāna is characterized as the 'path which leads to perfect enlightenment which may be termed as 'Anuttara Samyaka Sambodhi' in Sanskrit.¹²

With the evolution of the idea of the Vajrasattva, another new idea known as the theory of the five Dhyānī-Buddhas was introduced. The five Dhyānī-Buddhas are of five different families (Kulas) with their Śaktis. The families are Moha, presided over by the Dhyānī-Buddha Vairochana with his Sakti Vajradhātvisvari; Dveṣa, presided over by the Dhyānī-Buddha Aksobhya with his Śakti Lochanā;

Chintāmani, presided over by the Dhyānī-Buddha Ratnasambhava with his Śakti Māmaki; Rāga, presided over by the Dhyānī-Buddha Amitābha with his Śakti Pandarā and Samaya, presided over by the Dhyānī-Budha Amoghasiddhi with his Śakti Āryatārā. Thus for the first time, the worship of Śaktis was introduced into Buddhism by the Vajrayānists with which a host of elements including a large number of gods and goddesses, their Sādhanas, panegyrics, etc. were also found occupying suitable places in Buddhism.

Siddha Indrabhuti, the king of Uddiyāna is regarded as the propounder of Vajrayāna and to his authorship several tantric works of Vajrayānic importance are attributed, of which at least twenty-three are preserved in the pages of Tibetan *Tangyur* in translations. The *Jñānasiddhi*,¹³ one of the tantric texts composed by him in Sanskrit contains twenty-two chapters and brings to light numerous leading tenets and rites of Vajrayāna. This esteemed work opens with an invocation to Lord Jagannātha, in which Jagannātha has been prayed as Buddha. We also find mentions of Lord Jagannātha in four other verses of this work.

Sahajayāna

The literal meaning of the word *Sahaja* is that, which is inborn or which originates with the birth or origination of any entity (*Sahajāyate iti Sahaja*).¹⁴ The *Hevajra Tantra* also expresses the same connotation, i.e. that which accompanies with the birth is Sahaja. Dr. N.K. Sahu defines Sahajayāna in the following manner - The word *Sahaja* literally means that which accompanies with the birth and manifests itself as the primitive and natural propensities in man. The path that helps man to realise the truth through satisfying these inborn and fundamental propensities is therefore, the most natural and easiest of all paths and hence, it is called the *Sahaja* path or Sahajayāna." Dr. S.B. Dasgupta derives both the primary and the secondary meaning of the word *Sahaja* as "what is natural is the easiest and thus *Sahaja*, from its primary meaning of being natural, requires the secondary meaning of being easy, straight or plain. Thus Sahajayāna or *Sahaja* path is the easy or straight path which is called *Rājapatha* (royal road) by Sāntipāda.¹⁵ Lakṣminkarā or Bhagavati Lakṣmi is regarded as the propounder of Sahajayāna. She was the sister of Siddha Indrabhuti, the propounder of Vajrayāna. She

married the son of Jalendra, the king of Lankāpuri. was very bold in preaching them in a short but interesting work entitled Advayasiddhi. This new teaching could attract many people, who in due course, were turned into its upholders and were known as *Sahajiyās*, the teachings of Laksminkarā they followed being Sahajayāna This work reveals that she was influenced by the *Jñānasiddhi* composed by her brother to a great extent and as such was his favorite disciple.

In this work the authoress seems to have revolted against the systems of Vajrayāna. She boldly refused the worship of gods and goddesses which was a remarkable feature of Vajrayāna represented through the five Dhyāni-Buddhas and their innumerable emanations. She appears to be very bold when she "declares that no suffering, no fasting, no bathing, no purification, no other rules of society are necessary, nor do you need to bow down before the images of gods, which are prepared of wood, stone or mud; you should with concentration offer worship to your own body, where all gods reside."¹⁶

Kālacakrayāna

The word Kālacakra literally means the wheel of time. "The word Kala means time, death and destruction. Kālacakra is the wheel of destruction". opines Mm. Haraprasada Shastri and for this opinion he seems to be influenced by the idea expressed in the *Tantrāloka* (Chapter VI) of Abhinava Gupta.

The Lord then explained the secret Yoga which is not known to anybody else and which, with all the accessories of mystic circle (*maṇḍala*), resides within the body. Then the Lord added how all the universe with all the objects and localities were situated within the body and how time (*Kāla*) in its phases, viz day, night, fortnight, month, year, etc. are within the body in the process of the vital wind (*prāna-vayu*).

According to the *Laghukālacakra-tantrarāja-tikā* entitled *Vimalaprabhā*, the commentary of the *Kālacakra Tantra*, Kālacakra is a deity and an embodiment of *Sūnyatā* and *Karuṇā* and is embraced by the goddess Prajñā and represents the philosophical conception of advaya or non duality. He is regarded as the Ādi-Buddha or the progenitor even of the Buddhas, that is to say, the Dhyāni-Buddhas. He is in possession of three Kāyas, the knower of the three times (Tri-kāla - past, present and future), the omniscient. It is understood from the Kālacakra

She preached very peculiar and novel doctrines and Tantra that the maṇḍala (circle) of the deity is composed of all the planets and stars and the book, therefore, is directly connected with astronomy and astrology and thus astronomy and astrology came to be associated with the practice of Yoga, 38 The central deity Kālachakra, as indicated by the very name, is sanctioned by such minor deities, which represent time or time factor. Mañjusrī is attributed to be the introducer of the *Kālachakra Tantra* and one Puṇḍarika of the *Vimalaprabhā*, the commentary of the *Kālacakra Tantra*.

The Ratnagiri Vihara of Orissa played an important role in the emergence and development of the Kālacakratantra. Dr. Debala Mitra, a distinguished scholar has stated in this connection- "These Tibetan references would indicate that Ratnagiri became a renowned academic centre, noted for the spiritual inspiration and likely pursuit of the Kālacakra-tantra in the latter part of the tenth century A.D. The importance of this institution is attested by the fact that celebrated savants (like Naropā or Naro-pa, an elder contemporary of Atiśa Dipankara) and scholars of different parts of India resorted to this establishment for imparting and receiving Buddhist religion and philosophy. That Vajrayāna and its offshoot Kālacakrayana found a strong footing at Ratnagiri is fully corroborated by excavations which yielded, apart from religious edifices, numerous votive stupas with the reliefs of divinities of the Vajrayāna pantheon, separate images of these divinities and inscribed stone slabs and moulded terracotta plaques with dhāranīs. In the overwhelming number of votive *stupas*, Ratnagiri can even compete with Bodh-Gaya, the holiest of the Buddhist centres. The number of these antiquities is an adequate index of the profound popularity and sanctity of the centre in the Buddhist world."¹⁷

Uḍḍiyāna Pītha

Kamakhya, Sirihatṭa, Pūrṇagiri and Uḍḍiyāna are four tantric pīthas or places of tantric importance of the Vajrayānists as mentioned in the *Sādhanamālā*.¹⁸ Among those four pīthas Uḍḍiyāna is the most important pītha and most frequently mentioned by the Hindu Tantras alike. Most of the philosophers and scholars who are responsible

for the introduction and growth of Tantric Buddhism are found connected with the territory of

Uḍḍiyāna. Scholars are divided among themselves as to the location of Uḍḍiyāna, which is also spelt as Oḍḍiyāna, Oḍiyāna, Odrayana, etc. Mm. H.P. Shastri definitely placed it in Orissa. B. Bhattacharyya accepts this identification and further infers that Uḍḍiyāna, being one of the four pīṭhas sacred to the Vajrayānists, should be atleast near Kāmākhyā (Kāmṛūpa) and Śirihatṭa (Sylhet) in Assam and it is unusual to think that all these four pithas received their sanctity from the temples dedicated to Vajrayogini.

Dr. N.K. Sahu, in his monumental work Buddhism in Orissa has shown how the aforesaid scholars are mistaken in identifying the tantric pitha and by adducing strong arguments from traditional, historical, literary and epigraphical sources proved that Orissa was the most important tantric pīṭha, where Tántric Buddhism grew and developed and probably was transmitted to other three pithas - Kāmākhyā, Sirihatṭa and Pūrṇagiri and hence to the rest of India and ultimately beyond the sea.

Dr. K.C. Panigrahi, another historian of Orissa is not prepared to accept what Dr. Sahu has argued as to the identification of Uḍḍiyāna and places like Sambhala, Lankā, etc. connected with it.

Deities

Since Mahāyāna and Tantrayāna had a long career in Orissa, the evolution of a new pantheon of gods and goddesses in Buddhism gave full scope to the creative genius of the artists and sculptors of the early medieval Orissa, who shaped them in conformity with the widely varied Buddhist iconography and gave them a place of honour in the monasteries and other sanctuaries of Buddhist importance. Buddhist sites like Ratnagiri, Udayagiri, Lalitagiri, Kuruma, Achutrajpur, Aragarh, etc. have yielded icons belonging to Tantric Buddhism. Besides, a survey of the Prachi valley of Puri and Cuttack districts has brought to light so many gods and goddesses of Tantrayāna suggesting the prevalence of the pantheon in the entire valley.

In the Buddhist pantheon, Lokeśvara or Avalokiteśvara is very famous as a Bodhisattva, who emanates from the Dhyāni-Buddha Amitābha. At almost all the places of Orissa which were of Buddhist importance in the past, images of Avalokiteśvara of different varieties like Khasarapaṇa, Jaṭāmukutā,

Śimhanāda, Lokanātha, Śankhapāni, Śankhanātha, etc. are met with.

Padmapāni is a Bodhisattva, the icons of which are seen in abundance in Lalitagiri. An image of Padmapāni is found at the site of Ratnagiri. In the Hanumāna temple at Māhānga, an image of Padmapāni Bodhisattva is found. Such an image recovered from the village Bāneswarnāsi in the district of Cuttack is preserved in the Jayadeva Orissa State Museum. In the premises of F.M. College, Balasore such an image is also seen firmly planted to the ground. From the ruins of Buddhist establishment at Vajragiri in the district of Cuttack two images of Padmapāni have been shifted to the Orissa State Museum for proper preservation and display.

Yamāri (the enemy of Yama) is otherwise known as Yamāntaka (the destroyer of Yama) and is fierce in appearance. A dwarfish image recovered from Ratnagiri is a variety of Kṛṣṇayamāri. A metal image of this variety has also been discovered from the ruins of Ratnagiri. At Yamadharma-pīṭha of Kuruma in Puri district a Kṛṣṇayamāri is under active worship in the name of Yama.

Jambhala, the Buddhist god of wealth is seen at various Buddhist sites of Orissa. A worn-out Jambhala image is seen fixed to the wall of the inner gate of the Jagannātha temple at Baripada. On the outer wall of Ratnagiri Mahāvihāra there is an image of Jambhala. The recent excavation at Udayagiri has exposed an image of Jambhala. Two images of Jambhala are met with in the Prāchi valley - one in the village of Badatara near Gop and the other one smaller in size is found attached to the elevated chaurā wall of the Arkatīrtha Maṭha near Niali. In the bronze hoard recovered from Achutrājpur and subsequently housed in Jayadeva Orissa State Museum, one icon Jambhala is found preserved.

Vaiśravaṇa is a Yakṣa attendant of Jambhala, the god of wealth. From the brick mounds of Udayagiri an image of Vaiśravaṇa was acquired for the Indian Museum, Calcutta.

Pañchika is a Yakṣa and the consort of Hāriti. He resembles Jambhala in attributes as both of them are Yaksas. An image of Pañchika has been found at Ratnagiri.

Sambara is a ferocious god with a garland of skulls, three round eyes and the garment of tiger skin. An image of Sambara from Ratnagiri is seen now in the Patna Museum. It is twelve-armed and tramples

upon two Brahmanical deities, Bhairava and Kālaratri in the Alidha posture. Dr. Debala Mitra has discussed this deity at length in the Orissa Historical Research Journal, Vol. IX, Nos. 3 & 4.

The worship of the goddess Prajñāpāramitā was very popular among the Buddhists. At the Buddhist site of Ratnagiri a small image of Prajñāpāramitā is found. A life-size image of this goddess recovered from Baneravanasi near Narasinghpur has been lodged in the Padmesvara temple. At the time of renovation of Tāladandā canal at Tarapur, an image of this goddess has been discovered. In the village Betenda near Nayahata in the Prāchi valley, an image identified with Pita-Prajñāpāramitā is enshrined in a small temple.

Tārā is a common name applied to a large number of feminine deities in the Buddhist pantheon. In the published sādhanamālā, Jaṅguli, Parṇasavarī, Khadiravani and many others are called Tārā. Among the group of Buddhist images dug out at Solampur in Balasore district and fixed to the outer walls of the modern Raghunatha temple, there is one two-armed image of Tārā. Of the two icons of Tārā recovered from Baneravanasi, one has found its way to the Patna Museum. In the village of Kaupur in the district of Balasore, an image of Tārā is lying under a tree. Some figures of Tārā have been acquired for the Orissa State Museum from Ayodhyā in the district of Balasore. From the most promising site at Achutrajpur in the district of Puri an image of Tārā has been acquired and kept inside the premises of the Godāvarīśa Vidyāpīṭha.

Pāṇḍara, who is also known as Pandaravasini is the spiritual consort of the Dhyāni-Buddha Amitābha. An icon found in the Achutrajpur hoard is identified with Pāṇḍarā.

Nairātmā, a female deity worshipped by the Tantric Buddhists looks terrible with bare fangs, triple round eyes and a protruding tongue. An image of this deity has so far been discovered in a village named Tiruna in the Prachi valley.

Mārici is the Vajrayānic goddess of dawn. In Orissa the goddess is not rare at all. From Khadipada in the Balasore district the image of a Mārici has been shifted to the Indian Museum, Calcutta. Another image of Mārici is being worshipped as Jayadurgā in the village of Ayodhya of the same district. An image of Mārici which is learnt to have been brought from

Khiching is seen preserved in the small museum at Baripada.

Aparājītā is a ferocious deity whose right hand exhibits the act of dealing a slap. Her face is awful and terrible. She is represented as trampling upon the Hindu god Ganeśa. In the newly built museum at Lalitgiri an image of this deity is preserved. Another image of this deity, which has been recently found out at Udayagiri is broken and the upper portion is lost.

Kurukullā is also a tantric deity. The treasurers of Udayagiri include a figure of Kurukullā. The image of a Tarodbhava Kurukullā is found fixed to the inner wall of the Chandanamaṇḍapa at Kakatapur on the bank of the river Prachi. The image is worshipped as Nārāyani by the local people. In the bronze collections of Achutrajpur one comes across an Uddiyāna Kurukullā.

The goddess Bhṛkṭi is peaceful in appearance and blooms in youth. The bronze hoard from Achutrajpur contains two images of Bhṛkṭi. At some places she is also found at the side of Khasarpana Avalokitesvara as a companion deity. Vajravārāhī is the consort of Heruka and her union with Heruka constitutes the popular Buddhist Tantras, namely, the Cakrasambhara Tantra and the Vajravārāhī Tantra. The Late R.P. Chanda saw an image of this goddess in a modern temple at Chaudwar, which is now missing.

Vartāli is one of the four attendant goddesses of Mārīcī. An image of this deity has been unearthed from the debris of Ayodhya in the Balasore district. Vasudhārā is the consort of Jambhala, the Buddhist god of wealth. The treasures of Ratnagiri contain three images of Vasudhārā. The recent excavation at Lalitgiri has yielded an image of Vasudhārā.

Hāriti is a popular Buddhist goddess. She is recognised by her association with children. The treasures of Ratnagiri include one Hāriti image.

An icon of the goddess Chundā is seen worshipped in the name of Vāsuli Thākurani in Bania Sahi of the Cuttack town. As many as five bronze images of Chunda have been unearthed from the promising Buddhist site of Achutrajpur.

Conclusion:

In course of time Buddhism declined in Orissa and with its decline people lost all interest in it and, thus, the monasteries and other Buddhist establishments were abandoned, allowing them to be covered by dense vegetation. Thus the Buddhist plastic art

gradually died away. Later on Buddhism was supplanted by Saivism and at some Buddhist sites Saivite temples raised their heads. At some other places Buddhist deities were converted into Hindu deities and such instances are many.

The impact of Tantrayāna on the Oriya literature and Oriya society is manifold. The literature of Tantrayāna i.e., the Charyāgītis and Dohāgītis, etc. has influenced the Oriya poets from the fifteenth century A.D. till the modern time. The social customs depicted in that literature are still alive in the present day Oriya society. Tantra and Tantric culture, it is believed, will continue to cast their shadows on human life and behavior of Orissa for ages to come.

Thus Orissa had played an important role in the emergence and development of Tantrayāna, the last phase of Buddhism consisting of Vajrayāna, Sahajayāna and Kālachakrayāna, which influenced the Oriya literature and society to a marked extent and thereby formed part of the Orissa culture.

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